

Exploratory Analysis of the Factors Influencing Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) in Hospitals

Dr. Sangeetha Natarajan , Sumaya Sulaiman Rashid Al Farsi, Reem Dhahir Sulaiman Al Amri, Raida Salim Hamood Al Jamoodi, Wafa Rashid Hamed Al Shueili
University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Nizwa, Sultanate of Oman

Abstract

Since the ILO preamble in 1919, occupational safety and health have been key to ensuring safe workplaces and a strong preventive safety culture worldwide. Oman, an ILO member since 1994, has one of the best healthcare systems, offering free primary care for citizens and subsidized care for expatriates. As of 2023, Oman has 74 hospitals, 897 medical centers, and 6,409 medical professionals, with a hospital bed capacity of 14.9 per 10,000 people (National Centre for Statistics and Information). In 2014, Oman launched Health Vision 2050, a long-term strategy to build an efficient, equitable healthcare system through major investments (Oman Medical Journal, 2017). Today, hospitals focus on delivering high-quality care aligned with international standards, with an emphasis on education and research. However, work-related injuries, diseases, and accidents remain prevalent, leading to significant human and economic costs. This study explores factors affecting occupational health and safety in hospitals in the Ad Dakhliyah region, Oman. Using a mixed-method approach with surveys and interviews, it examines ways to reduce workplace risks and hazards. The findings were analyzed statistically to provide meaningful conclusions and recommendations.

Keywords: *Occupational Health, Safety, Hazards, Risks, Healthcare, Hospitals.*

Suggested citation: Natarajan, S., Al Farsi, S.S.R., Al Amri, R.D.S., Al Jamoodi, R.S.H., & Al Shueili, W.R.H. (2025). Exploratory Analysis of the Factors Influencing Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) in Hospitals. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 45-56. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(2).05

Introduction

Under Oman Vision 2040, the Ministry of Health plays a key role in shaping the nation's healthcare system, integrating strategies into five-year development plans. In early 2023, it submitted a performance report to guide future healthcare investments (Qasem Al Salmi et al., 2024). Oman has made remarkable progress in healthcare, earning global recognition for reducing infant mortality rates (Al Dhawi et al., 2007). To enhance patient safety, Oman adopted the WHO's Patient Safety Friendly Hospital Initiative (PSFHI), with 11 hospitals participating in 2016 through structured planning, training, and evaluations (Ahmed Al-Mandhari et al., 2018). The government has invested \$275 million in healthcare projects, including new hospitals, expansions, and specialized units to improve accessibility and efficiency (Times of Oman, 2021). Notable projects include the \$1.5 billion Sultan Qaboos Medical City in Muscat and the \$1 billion International Medical City in Salalah, both aimed at strengthening healthcare services and boosting medical tourism. Oman has also embraced digital transformation, linking 86% of government hospitals to a central electronic database by 2015, streamlining healthcare services and reducing patient wait times. Despite economic challenges, the ninth five-year plan (2016–2020) prioritized developing medical cities, investing in healthcare professionals, and restructuring medical education (Oxford Business Group).

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) remains essential for the worker's well-being. The Joint ILO/WHO Committee defines OHS as protecting workers from hazards while promoting overall health and safety, aiming to prevent workplace accidents and risks (Pierre Vincensini). Occupational health and safety (OHS) aim to prevent workplace hazards, ensuring a safe environment for employees. OHS programs include policies and procedures to minimize accidents, injuries, and work-related illnesses. These measures can be statutory or non-statutory, but their main goal is workplace safety. In hospitals, where risks are high, proactive measures are essential. Hospital workers face various hazards (NASP, 2023) say Physical Hazards, Biological Hazards, Chemical Hazards, Ergonomic Risks, Psychological threats. While these hazards pose serious risks, they can be reduced by integrating OHS practices into daily hospital operations.

This study explores key challenges, evaluates existing safety measures, and identifies strategies to enhance workplace safety, ultimately benefiting both employees and patients. Thereby the present study explores the following research questions:

1. How do physical, psychosocial, and individual factors impact OHS in hospitals?
2. Does workplace organization influence OHS practices in these hospitals?
3. How does ergonomics contribute to OHS in hospitals?
4. What measures can help reduce hospital workplace hazards?

Literature Review

While numerous studies on Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) in hospitals exist globally, research in Oman's healthcare sector remains limited. International studies emphasize the importance of workplace safety, the role of hospital management in implementing OHS programs, and the impact of training on reducing workplace hazards.

Occupational Safety and Health in Hospitals Outside Oman

Vredenburgh AG. (2002), stressed that the safety of the workers, doctors, nurses, technicians, workers, patients and visitors is the cornerstone of occupational care, safety and health in the hospital. It is the Department of Occupational Safety and Security System, that bears the responsibility. Its duties are to manage, to guide, to plan, to implement and to follow-up the occupational security and safety in the organization. Gimeno D, Felknor S, Burau KD, Delclos GL. (2005), studied occupational safety and suggested ways on maintaining sound and secure work in hospital environment. The results show that occupational safety and health contribute to reducing the rates of work accidents and injuries, protecting them from diseases and impairments, and preserving physical and psychological capabilities. Manyele, Ngonyani, Eliakimu (2008) conducted a study to assess the status of occupational health and safety (OHS) in Tanzanian hospitals and identified the key areas of intervention. Occupational hazards exist wherever health care is practiced. Nefise Bahcecik and Havva Ozturk (2009) examined the problems in relation to occupational health, assessed occupational safety precautions and the applications of a private hospital as well as a university hospital.

Prof. Dr. Najm Al-Azzawi and Prof. Dr. Abbas Hussein Jawad (2010) examined the importance of health and safety for workers in their institutions. The management of organizations has increased its interest nowadays in determining the level of protection that it should provide to its employees. A hospital-based cross-sectional study was undertaken in a tertiary private hospital in Karnataka, Bangalore, India by Phukan.P in 2014, in which the awareness of occupational safety measures, biomedical waste handling, disposal and its compliance in their daily practice was examined. Nuwayhid (2016), in his study on Occupational health and safety in hospitals accreditation system, assessed the relationship between the status of accreditation among private Lebanese hospitals and compliance with OHS accreditation standards. The results were that accredited hospitals reported statistically better OHS performance than non-accredited hospitals based on the standards outlined in the accreditation manual. Rima R. Habib,

Ghandour Blanche, Fares Souha, Fadi El-Jardali, and Iman Nazanin Izadi and Reza Piruznia (2018) in their research study found out that hospital staffs are exposed to a wide range of health hazards in their workplace that are mainly biological, chemical, physical, ergonomic and psychological in nature.

Sarah Mossburg, Angela Agore, Manka Nkimberg, Yvonne (2019) in their study on “Occupational Hazards among Healthcare Workers in Africa: A Systematic Review” found out that workers in sub-Saharan Africa have higher rates of occupational exposure to infectious diseases than workers in developed countries. Prajwal MS, Kundury KK, Sujay MJ (2020) assessed the awareness on occupational safety and health hazards among nursing staff of a teaching hospital. Rasiah, Jaafar, Yusof, Ponnudurai, KatrinaPooi Yin Chung, Sasikala Devi (2020) assessed the level of trust between patients and healthcare providers, its dimensions and determinants. Imran Aslan (2021) studied the ranking and comparing occupational health and safety system performance indicators in hospitals by the analytic hierarchy process. Philip Apraku et al (2022), identified the occupational health hazards among healthcare providers and ancillary staff in Ghana. Takalani Denge and Mahlasela Rakhudu (2022), explored and described the perceptions of nurses on occupational health hazards and safety practices in Ditsobotla public hospitals of Northwest province. Ramita Marasini, Pratik Shrestha, Yaman Chaudhary (2023) stressed the fact that occupational health and safety is a broad discipline that covers several specialized fields, including physical, psychological, chemical, biological, and mechanical/electrical, and assesses the health and safety of employees in a broader context.

Research Studies in Healthcare in Oman

Asma S. Al Yahyaei (2009) studied the factors determining the level of job satisfaction of Registered nurses in Muscat and the relationships to Herzberg’s motivation and hygiene factors. The findings proved that motivation factors and hygiene factors are significantly correlated with job satisfaction. Khamis N. Al-Gharbi, Said M. Gattoufi, Ali H. Al-Badi, Ali A. Al-Hashmi (2015), presented a case study of the project management of Al-Shifa healthcare information system (HIS) in Oman. Firdouse Rahman Khan, Sheikh Mohammed Ali Al-Balushi (2017), analyzed the factors influencing patients to go to private hospitals against public hospitals of Oman and their expectations of patients in the integrated public hospitals in Oman. In a study conducted by Muna Habib AL Lawati, Stephanie D. Short, Nadia Noor Abdulhadi, Sathiya Murthi Panchatcharam and Sarah Dennis (2019), the participants rated patient safety in the primary health care setting as excellent and the perception of patient safety was positive. Humaid Al-Kalbani, Tariq Al-Saadi, Ahmed Al-Kumzari, Hassan Al-Bahrani (2020), indicated that there are no standards to measure patient satisfaction and most of the developed countries have well-structured health care systems. Fatma Al-Jabri, Tarja Kvist, Reijo Sund and Hannele Turunen(2021), conducted a study to examine the perspectives of patients’ and healthcare professionals’ on overall quality of care and patient safety standards at two tertiary hospitals in Oman. They tried to identify the demographic characteristics that are related to the overall quality of care and patient safety.

Overall, while global research underscores the significance of OHS in hospitals, Omani studies have focused more on patient care than occupational safety. This gap highlights the need for further investigation into OHS challenges specific to Oman’s healthcare sector, ensuring better protection for healthcare workers and improved safety standards.

Methodology

This research follows a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative (employee interviews) and quantitative (structured surveys) methods to assess occupational health and safety (OHS) practices in hospitals across Ad Dakhliyah. As an exploratory study, it seeks to identify key factors physical, psychological, individual, organizational, and ergonomic—that influence OHS in the region. The sampling design includes hospitals from major regions in Ad Dakhliyah, such as Nizwa, Bahla, Adam, Izki, and Samail. The study covers all government and private hospitals in these areas, with a total of six hospitals forming the research population. A multistage sampling technique is used, beginning with area sampling to categorize hospitals by location, followed by quota and convenience sampling to ensure

proportional and accessible sample selection. Data for the study is collected from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data is obtained through structured questionnaires and interviews with hospital employees, while secondary data is gathered from relevant published and unpublished reports. The collected data is analyzed using various statistical tools. Descriptive statistics summarize key variables through percentage analysis, while correlation analysis examines the influence of gender, age, and department on OHS practices, in the Ad Dakhliyah region, Oman.

Results and Implications

Descriptive Statistics of Independent and Dependent Variables

Demographic Profile

Most participants in the study were female (66%) and primarily belonged to the 25–31 age group (58%). Most respondents were Omani nationals (63%).

Table 1. Physical Factors Influencing the OHS Practices in Hospitals

Physical factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (4)	Strongly Disagree (5)
Manual handling of materials (hazardous chemicals, gas cylinders etc)	180 (51.43%)	90 (25.71%)	50 (14.29%)	30 (8.57%)	0 (0%)
Frequent lifting of patients and handling postures	170 (48.57%)	120 (34.29%)	60 (17.14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Transferring and repositioning of patients and musculoskeletal injury	170 (48.57%)	110 (31.43%)	40 (11.43%)	20 (5.71%)	10 (2.86%)
Work pressure, malfunctioning machines	150 (42.86%)	140 (40%)	40 (11.43%)	20 (5.71%)	0 (0%)
Unfamiliar tasks, failure to wear gloves and protective equipment	140 (40%)	130 (37.14%)	20 (5.71%)	40 (11.43%)	20 (5.71%)
Exposed to ergonomic and safety hazards from manual handling	170 (48.57%)	110 (31.43%)	30 (8.57%)	40 (11.43%)	0 (0%)

The findings highlight key occupational health and safety (OHS) concerns in hospitals, particularly related to manual handling, patient lifting, and ergonomic hazards. A significant majority (77.14%) agree that manual handling of materials is a critical factor in hospital safety, while an even larger percentage (82.86%) recognize frequent patient lifting as a major physical strain on healthcare workers. Similarly, 80% believe that transferring and repositioning patients poses a substantial risk to workplace safety. Work pressure and malfunctioning machines were also identified as major concerns, with 82.86% acknowledging their impact on OHS. Additionally, 77.14% of respondents believe that unfamiliar tasks and failure to wear protective equipment affect workplace safety, though a notable 17.14% expressed disagreement, suggesting some variation in perceptions. Ergonomic risks from manual handling were another significant issue, with 80% of respondents agreeing on their importance. Overall, the most pressing risks identified were manual handling, patient lifting, transferring patients, and ergonomic hazards, with over 75% agreement on their impact. Unfamiliar tasks and failure to wear protective equipment received slightly lower concern, with more respondents expressing mixed views. Given these findings, hospitals should prioritize improving safety measures related to manual handling, patient lifting, and ergonomic hazards. Additionally, addressing secondary concerns, such as proper training for unfamiliar tasks and ensuring consistent use of protective equipment, can further enhance workplace safety and support the well-being of healthcare professionals.

Table 2. Psychosocial Factors Influencing the OHS Practices in Hospitals

Psychosocial factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (4)	Strongly Disagree (5)
Work intensification	140 (40%)	160 (45.71%)	30 (8.57%)	20 (5.71%)	0 (0%)
Highly monotonous work	110 (31.43%)	160 (45.71%)	50 (14.29%)	0 (0%)	30 (8.57%)
Time pressure or deadlines	170 (48.57%)	140 (40%)	30 (8.57%)	0 (0%)	10 (2.86%)
Significant mental workload	120 (34.29%)	150 (42.86%)	50 (14.29%)	20 (5.71%)	10 (2.86%)
Less /Weak supervisor support	110 (31.43%)	130 (37.14%)	70 (20%)	0 (0%)	40 (11.43%)
Job insecurity	120 (34.29%)	110 (31.43%)	100 (28.57%)	10 (2.86%)	10 (2.86%)

The study highlights key psychosocial factors affecting occupational health and safety (OHS) in hospitals, based on respondents' perceptions. Time pressure and deadlines (88.57%) and work intensification (85.71%) emerged as the most significant concerns, with most employees agreeing that heavy workloads and tight deadlines negatively impact workplace safety. Other notable issues included monotonous work (77.14%), significant mental workload (77.15%), and weak supervisor support (68.57%), though responses varied. While most acknowledged these as important, some respondents expressed neutrality or disagreement, suggesting differences in workplace experiences. Job insecurity (65.72%) had the highest percentage of neutral responses (28.57%), indicating that its impact may depend on individual job roles. To improve OHS in hospitals, efforts should focus on reducing time pressure, managing workloads more effectively, and alleviating excessive mental strain. Strengthening supervisor support and addressing job security concerns can also contribute to a healthier and safer work environment for healthcare professionals.

Table 3. Work Organizing Factors Influencing the OHS Practices in Hospitals

Work organising factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (4)	Strongly Disagree (5)
Interference of day and night shift decreases the efficiency of workers	140 (40%)	140 (40%)	50 (14.29%)	0 (0%)	20 (5.71%)
Workers with rotating shifts often experience sleep deficits and fatigue	150 (42.86%)	170 (48.57%)	10 (2.86%)	10 (2.86%)	10 (2.86%)
Night workers have higher risk for injury	140 (40%)	120 (34.29%)	50 (14.29%)	20 (5.71%)	20 (5.71%)
Increased risk is linked to working overtime, long hours and 7-hour shifts	140 (40%)	80 (22.86%)	90 (25.71%)	20 (5.71%)	20 (5.71%)
Work-related problems cause a reduced labor force	80 (22.86%)	190 (54.29%)	30 (8.57%)	0 (0%)	50 (14.29%)

The study highlights the impact of work schedules on occupational health and safety (OHS) in hospitals. Rotating shifts (91.43%) and shift interference (80%) were identified as major concerns, with most respondents agreeing that frequent schedule changes and disrupted shifts negatively affect worker efficiency and well-being. Other significant factors included night shifts (74.29%) and work-related problems affecting workforce efficiency (77.15%), though some respondents remained neutral or disagreed, suggesting that experiences vary among employees. Extended working hours (62.86%) had the highest level of neutrality (25.71%), indicating mixed perceptions of their impact on health and safety.

To improve OHS, hospitals should focus on minimizing shift-related fatigue, addressing night shift injury risks, and finding ways to reduce the negative effects of rotating schedules. Additionally, further research into the varying perceptions of overtime risks can help create a safer and more supportive work environment for healthcare professionals.

Table 4. Individual Factors Influencing the OHS Practices in Hospital

Individual factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (4)	Strongly Disagree (5)
More injuries are being reported among younger workers	40 (11.43%)	210 (60%)	60 (17.14%)	20 (5.71%)	20 (5.71%)
More injuries are being reported among workers with lower educational attainment	110 (31.43%)	110 (31.43%)	50 (14.29%)	40 (11.43%)	40 (11.43%)
Increased risks are being observed among beginner workers	70 (20%)	120 (34.29%)	110 (31.43%)	40 (11.43%)	10 (2.86%)
Experienced workers plan, limit fatigue, avoid stressful and emergency situations	70 (20%)	90 (25.71%)	50 (14.29%)	120 (34.29%)	20 (5.71%)
Male workers are more capable in handling equipment, heavy material, and patients	180 (51.43%)	80 (22.86%)	20 (5.71%)	40 (11.43%)	71 (8.57%)

71.43% believe younger workers are more injury-prone, suggesting a perception of inexperience as a risk factor, while 17.14% remain neutral. 62.86% link lower education levels with higher injury rates, but 22.86% disagree, reflecting differing views on education's role in workplace safety. 54.29% agree that new employees face higher risks, though 31.43% are neutral, indicating inconsistency in perceptions. 45.71% believe experienced workers avoid risks better, while 40% disagree, showing mixed opinions. 74.29% perceive male workers as more capable in managing tasks, but 20% disagree, indicating potential for more inclusive perspectives on gender roles in safety.

Correlation Analysis Studying the Influence of Gender on Physical, Psychological, Work Organization and Individual Factors of OHS Practices in Hospitals in Ad Dakhliyah Region

Null Hypothesis (H₀):

There is no significant correlation between Gender of employees and physical, psychological, work organization, individual factors and OHS practices in hospitals in Ad Dakhliyah region.

Table 5. Correlation Analysis Studying the Influence of Gender on Influencing Factors of OHS Practices in Hospitals

Physical factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
Manual handling of materials	9.554080	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Frequent lifting of patients and handling postures	0.016578	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Transferring and repositioning of patients and musculoskeletal injury	4.63250	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Work pressure, malfunctioning machines	4.104324	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Unfamiliar tasks, failure to wear gloves and protective equipment	1.955744	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Exposed to ergonomic and safety hazards from manual handling	0.076022	Not Correlated (Accept Null Hypothesis)
Power tools and equipment, noise, confined spaces and electricity	1.297535	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Handling of dangerous substances	0.000607	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Performance of physical jobs in isolation	4.532771	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)

Long and variable working hours	1.902373	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Psychosocial factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
Work intensification	3.916405	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Highly monotonous work	5.872864	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Time pressure or deadlines	1.100539	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Significant mental workload	9.920694	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Less /Weak supervisor support	1.401887	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Job insecurity	2.886291	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Work organizing factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
Interference of day and night shift decreases the efficiency of workers	0.07271	Not Correlated (Accept Null Hypothesis)
Workers with rotating shifts often experience sleep deficits and fatigue	1.76001	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Night workers have higher risk for injury	0.00896	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Increased risk is linked to working overtime, long hours and 7-hour shifts	1.28242	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Work-related problems cause reduced labor force	0.00061	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Individual factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
More injuries are being reported among younger workers	2.360872	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
More injuries are being reported among workers with lower educational attainment	4.606313	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Increased risks are being observed among beginner workers	1.131729	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Experienced workers plan, limit fatigue, avoid stressful and emergency situations	0.000261	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Male workers are more capable in handling equipment, heavy material, and patients	9.507523	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)

The analysis shows a significant correlation between gender and most physical, psychological, work organization, and individual factors that influence OHS practices in hospitals. However, exposure to ergonomic and safety hazards from manual handling and interference between day and night shifts do not show a notable link to gender. These findings suggest that gender plays a crucial role in how employees perceive and navigate OHS-related challenges in hospital settings. This highlights the importance of implementing gender-sensitive policies and interventions to ensure workplace safety measures are inclusive and effectively address the unique experiences of all employees.

Correlation Analysis Studying the Influence of Age on Physical, Psychological, Work Organization and Individual Factors of OHS Practices in Hospitals in Ad Dakhliyah Region

Null Hypothesis (H₀):

There is no significant correlation between Age of employees and physical, psychological, work organization, individual factors and OHS practices in hospitals in Ad Dakhliyah region.

Table 6. Correlation Analysis Studying the Influence of Age on Influencing Factors of OHS Practices in Hospitals

Physical factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
Manual handling of materials	4.91959	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Frequent lifting of patients and handling postures	7.33391	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Transferring and repositioning of patients and musculoskeletal injury	5.55669	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Work pressure, malfunctioning machines	3.97254	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)

Unfamiliar tasks, failure to wear gloves and protective equipment	6.93650	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Exposed to ergonomic and safety hazards from manual handling	1.17574	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Power tools and equipment, noise, confined spaces and electricity	4.59597	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Handling of dangerous substances	1.67986	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Performance of physical jobs in isolation	4.38058	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Long and variable working hours	6.86500	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Psychosocial factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
Work intensification	4.90998	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Highly monotonous work	4.09613	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Time pressure or deadlines	1.00668	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Significant mental workload	1.83217	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Less /Weak supervisor support	3.37907	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Job insecurity	1.44117	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Work organizing factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
Interference of day and night shift decreases the efficiency of workers	8.62315	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Workers with rotating shifts often experience sleep deficits and fatigue	4.26205	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Night workers have higher risk for injury	3.85050	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Increased risk is linked to working overtime, long hours and 7-hour shifts	6.61577	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Work-related problems cause reduced labor force	5.76338	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Individual factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
More injuries are being reported among younger workers	1.46625	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
More injuries are being reported among workers with lower educational attainment	2.63528	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Increased risks are being observed among beginner workers	2.47244	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Experienced workers plan, limit fatigue, avoid stressful and emergency situations	1.97770	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Male workers are more capable in handling equipment, heavy material, and patients	1.49824	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)

The analysis reveals a significant correlation between age and various factors influencing occupational health and safety (OHS) practices in hospitals across the Ad Dakhliyah region. These factors include physical and psychological aspects, work organization, and individual characteristics. The findings highlight that age plays a crucial role in shaping how these elements impact employees' health and safety.

Given these insights, it is essential to develop age-specific policies in OHS management to address the distinct needs and challenges faced by different age groups. For example:

- Younger employees may require additional training and support to minimize the risk of workplace injuries.
- Older employees might benefit from modified workloads or ergonomic adjustments to alleviate physical strain.

These results underscore the importance of incorporating age diversity into OHS strategies to create a safer and more supportive hospital environment for all employees.

Correlation Analysis studying the influence of Nationality on physical, psychological, Work organization and individual factors of OHS practices in hospitals in Ad Dakhliyah region

Null Hypothesis (H₀):

There is no significant correlation between the Nationality of employees and physical, psychological, work organization, individual factors and OHS practices in hospitals in Ad Dakhliyah region.

Table 7. Correlation Analysis Studying the Influence of Nationality on Influencing Factors of OHS Practices in Hospitals

Physical factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
Manual handling of materials	1.44600	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Frequent lifting of patients and handling postures	3.18317	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Transferring and repositioning of patients and musculoskeletal injury	1.65412	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Work pressure, malfunctioning machines	0.00076	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Unfamiliar tasks, failure to wear gloves and protective equipment	0.00265	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Exposed to ergonomic and safety hazards from manual handling	0.26956	Not Correlated (Accept Null Hypothesis)
Power tools and equipment, noise, confined spaces and electricity	3.59406	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Handling of dangerous substances	2.89181	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Performance of physical jobs in isolation	0.00258	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Long and variable working hours	3.19275	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Psychosocial factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
Work intensification	4.3881	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Highly monotonous work	0.0032	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
2.C. Time pressure or deadlines	4.6638	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
2.D. Significant mental workload	1.5437	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
2.E. Less /Weak supervisor support	1.4273	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
2.F. Job insecurity	3.9554	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Work organizing factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
Interference of day and night shift decreases the efficiency of workers	1.29297	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Workers with rotating shifts often experience sleep deficits and fatigue	4.53313	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Night workers have higher risk for injury	2.6923	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Increased risk is linked to working overtime, long hours and 7-hour shifts	2.4796	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Work-related problems cause reduced labor force	1.92478	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Individual factors influencing the OHS practices in Hospitals.	P VALUE	Result
More injuries are being reported among younger workers	4.6337	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
More injuries are being reported among workers with lower educational attainment	5.8201	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Increased risks are being observed among beginner workers	1.2956	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Experienced workers plan, limit fatigue, avoid stressful and emergency situations	2.1284	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)
Male workers are more capable in handling equipment, heavy material, and patients	0.0004	Correlated (Reject Null Hypothesis)

The analysis indicates a significant correlation between nationality and most factors influencing occupational health and safety (OHS) practices in hospitals across the Ad Dakhliyah region. These factors include physical and psychological aspects, work organization, and individual characteristics. However, the study found no significant link between nationality and ergonomic or safety hazards related to manual handling. These findings highlight the need to consider employees' nationality when developing and

implementing OHS policies in hospitals. Workers from different national backgrounds may encounter unique challenges due to cultural differences, language barriers, or varying skill levels, which can impact their ability to perform certain tasks or adapt to workplace conditions. To address these differences, tailored OHS interventions may include:

- Training programs are designed to overcome cultural or language barriers.
- Adjustments to job roles or responsibilities based on employees' physical capabilities or educational backgrounds.
- Improved communication and support systems to foster inclusivity and enhance the effectiveness of OHS practices for a diverse workforce.

Conclusion

This study examines key factors affecting Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) practices in hospitals in the Al Dhakilya region, focusing on physical, psychosocial, work organization, and individual influences. The analysis identifies significant weaknesses in OHS, particularly regarding gender, age, nationality, and departmental challenges. Key issues include high injury risks for younger employees, physical strain on older workers, inadequate training for non-national employees, gender disparities, inconsistent workload distribution, long working hours, shift fatigue, weak supervisor support, and psychosocial stressors. To improve workplace safety, reduce risks, and enhance employee well-being, several key areas in hospital settings need attention.

- First, physical factors such as manual handling and unsafe work conditions must be addressed. Implementing ergonomic training, regular equipment maintenance, and mandatory use of protective gear can reduce injury risks. Additionally, investing in automated patient-lifting devices can minimize physical strain on healthcare workers.
- Second, work organization improvements are necessary to manage long hours, shift issues, and overtime. Hospitals should adopt fair shift scheduling, provide sufficient rest breaks, introduce rotational policies to balance workloads, and encourage staffing adjustments to reduce reliance on overtime.
- Third, psychosocial factors like stress, mental load, and weak supervision require careful management. Training supervisors in effective leadership, establishing mental health programs, offering career development opportunities, and implementing task rotation can enhance job satisfaction and prevent burnout.
- Fourth, specific attention should be given to high-risk groups, such as young, inexperienced, and night-shift employees. Specialized safety training, enhanced support, and mentorship for these workers can reduce injury risks. Onboarding safety programs and improved supervision for night shifts will further safeguard vulnerable workers.
- Finally, strengthening safety management and OHS strategies is essential. Developing comprehensive risk management frameworks, implementing regular and practical OHS training, ensuring compliance with safety regulations, and improving data tracking systems will lead to more effective hazard prevention. Introducing safety incentive programs can also foster a culture of safety awareness. By addressing these key areas: manual handling, work organization, mental health, injury risks, and safety management, hospitals can create a safer, more supportive work environment, ultimately improving employee well-being, job satisfaction, and healthcare efficiency.

References

Al-Azzawi, N., & Jawad, A. H. (2010). *Egyptian Journal of Social Work*, 8(1).

- Al-Gharbi, K. N., Gattoufi, S. M., Al-Badi, A. H., & Al-Hashmi, A. A. (2015). Al-Shifa healthcare information system in Oman: A debatable implementation success. *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 66(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1681-4835.2015.tb00473.x>
- Al-Jabri, F., Kvist, T., Sund, R., & Turunen, H. (2021). Quality of care and patient safety at healthcare institutions in Oman: Quantitative study of the perspectives of patients and healthcare professionals. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21(1), 1109. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-021-07152-2>
- Al-Kalbani, H., Al-Saadi, T., Al-Kumzari, A., & Al-Bahrani, H. (2020). Public's perception and satisfaction on the healthcare system in Sultanate of Oman: A cross-sectional study. *Annals of the National Academy of Medical Sciences (India)*, 56(4), 214–219.
- Al-Lawati, M. H., Short, S. D., Abdulhadi, N. N., Panchatcharam, S. M., & Dennis, S. (2019). Assessment of patient safety culture in primary health care in Muscat, Oman: A questionnaire-based survey. *BMC Family Practice*, 20(1), 50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-019-0932-4>
- Apraku, P., Akweongo, P., & Adjuik, M. (2022). Occupational health hazards among healthcare providers and ancillary staff in Ghana: A scoping review. *BMJ Open*, 12(10), e064499. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2022-064499>
- Bahcecik, N., & Ozturk, H. (2009). The occupational safety and health in hospitals from the point of nurses. *Research Gate Publications*, 33(4), 1205–1214.
- Denge, T., & Rakhudu, M. (2022). Perceptions of nurses on occupational health hazards and safety practices in Ditsobotla public hospitals in North West province. *Curationis*, 45(1), e1–e9. <https://doi.org/10.4102/curationis.v45i1.2346>
- Gimeno, D., Felknor, S., Burau, K. D., & Delclos, G. L. (2005). Organizational and occupational risk factors associated with work-related injuries among public hospital employees in Costa Rica. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 62(5), 337–343. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oem.2004.015750>
- Habib, R. R., Ghandour, B., Fares, S., El-Jardali, F., & Nuwayhid, I. (2016). Occupational health and safety in hospitals accreditation system: The case of Lebanon. *International Journal of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 22(3), 201–210. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10773525.2016.1172254>
- Hämäläinen, P., Takala, J., & Saarela, K. L. (2006). Global estimates of occupational accidents. *Safety Science*, 44(2), 137–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2005.08.017>
- International Labour Organization. (2013). International labour standards on occupational safety and health. Retrieved from <https://www.ilo.org/global/standards/subjects-covered-by-international-labour-standards/occupational-safety-and-health/lang-en/index.htm>
- Izadi, N., & Piruznia, R. (2018). Occupational health hazards among health care workers. *Public Health Open Access*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.23880/phoa-16000120>
- Khan, F. R., & Al-Balushi, S. M. A. (2017). Factors influencing the preference of private hospitals to public hospitals in Oman. *International Journal of Management*, 3(2), 67–77.
- Manyele, S. V., Ngonyani, H. A., & Eliakimu, E. (2008). The status of occupational safety among health service providers in hospitals in Tanzania. *Tanzania Journal of Health Research*, 10(3), 159–167. <https://doi.org/10.4314/thrb.v10i3.14347>
- Marasini, R., Shrestha, P., & Chaudhary, Y. (2023). Occupational health and safety hazards faced by healthcare professionals in Kathmandu-based hospitals: A cross-sectional analytical study. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 10(2), 593–603. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20230273>
- Ministry of Health. (2014). *Health Vision 2050*. Muscat: Ministry of Health. Retrieved from <https://www.moh.gov.om/documents/16506/119833/Health+Vision+2050/7b6f40f3-8f93-4397-9fde-34e04026b829>

- Ministry of Health. (2018). *Annual health report 2018*. Muscat: Ministry of Health. Retrieved from <https://www.moh.gov.om/en/web/statistics/annual-reports>
- Mossburg, S., Agore, A., Nkimbeng, M., & Commodore-Mensah, Y. (2019). Occupational hazards among healthcare workers in Africa: A systematic review. *Annals of Global Health*, 85(1), 78. <https://doi.org/10.5334/aogh.2419>
- National Association of Safety Professionals. (2023). Types of hazards. Retrieved from <https://naspweb.com/blog/types-of-hazards/>
- National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH), Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). (2022). Workplace safety and health topics. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/topics/default.html>
- Occupational health definition and meaning. (n.d.). *Collins English Dictionary*. Retrieved from <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/occupational-health>
- Oman Medical Journal. (2017). 32(2), 86–96. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5397084/>
- Oxford Business Group. (2017). *The Report: Oman 2017*. Retrieved from <https://oxfordbusinessgroup.com/reports/oman/2017-report>
- Phukan, P. (2014). Compliance to occupational safety measures among the paramedical workers in a tertiary hospital in Karnataka, South India. *International Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 4(1), 40–50.
- Prajwal, M. S., Kundury, K. K., & Sujay, M. J. (2020). Assessing the awareness on occupational safety and health hazards among nursing staff of a teaching hospital. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 9(12), 5961–5965. <https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpe.jfmpe.1295.20>
- Rasiah, S., Jaafar, S., Yusof, S., et al. (2020). A study of the nature and level of trust between patients and healthcare providers, its dimensions and determinants: A scoping review protocol. *BMJ Open*, 10(e028061). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-028061>
- Vredenburg, A. G. (2002). Organizational safety: Which management practices are most effective in reducing employee injury rates? *Journal of Safety Research*, 33(2), 259–276. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4375\(02\)00014-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4375(02)00014-6)
- World Health Organization. (2022). Occupational health. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/health-topics/occupational-health>
- World Health Organization. (2022). Occupational health: Health workers. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/occupational-health-health-workers>
- Yahyaie, A. S. A. (2009). *Job satisfaction of registered nurses in Muscat, Sultanate of Oman* (Master's thesis). California State University, Long Beach.

